

Liquefaction-induced Ground Damage Severity Index Map for Yangon City

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ABSTRACT

Yangon City is closely located from the main right-lateral strike-slip Sagaing fault and fallen in moderate to high seismic prone area. The aim of this paper is to examine the impact of ground damage to the existing Liquefaction Effect Index (I_L) based calibrations to produce the index map for various engineering purpose, using the classes size of Damage Severity Index (DSI). The data set that was analysed is compiled by borings with SPT from liquefied and non-liquefied sites in Yangon. The result is presented in the form of degree of colors range map that correspond to the values of I_L and DSI. As the majority of the sites in the city are of reclaimed land, vulnerability of liquefaction is observed to be very high at many places. According to the data, the Southern part of Yangon City is more damaged than the Northern part. Liquefaction-induced Ground Damage Severity Map will aid in avoiding possible problem areas for project locations and will also be a guide for further analysis of specific sites where liquefaction is probable.

Keywords: Liquefaction, I_L , DSI map.

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INTRODUCTION

Scientifically, liquefaction is a well understood mechanism. Using in-situ tests and soil parameters, the potential for occurrence can be relatively well predicted. However, the unique aspects of soil deposits require site testing at individual locations to determine the specific liquefaction potential. Liquefaction is a phenomenon in which the strength and stiffness of a soil is reduced by earthquake shaking or other rapid loading. Liquefaction occurs in saturated soils mostly of sand, that is, soils in which the space between individual particles is completely filled with water. This water exerts a pressure on the soil particles that influences how tightly the particles themselves are pressed together. Prior to an earthquake, the water pressure is relatively low. However, the cyclic loading due to an earthquake shaking can cause the water pressure to increase to the point where the soil particles can readily move with respect to each other, so called quick sand condition. When liquefaction occurs, the strength of the soil decreases mostly up to zero and, the ability of a soil deposit to support foundations for buildings and bridges are totally disappeared and caused severe damages to the structures on it. According to the investigated results for a lot of earthquakes that were experienced in the world, it is said that the followings are favorable conditions to occur the liquefaction (Tun Naing, 2014).

- (1) Lower fine content of saturated soil (Fine content is meant the size less than 0.06 mm)
- (2) Lower SPT blow count (N) of saturated sandy soil
- (3) Shallow groundwater table
- (4) Bigger maximum peak acceleration

Seismic hazard in Myanmar and particularly for Yangon area in question has been researched extensively. Yangon is one of the cities of Myanmar and the former capital, can said that low to medium seismicity based on the seismicity and the records of the previous considerably high magnitude earthquakes. Some of the large earthquakes that caused the considerable damages to some buildings and some casualties in and around Yangon Region can be recognized in the past records, e.g. the magnitude 7.3, earthquake that struck on May 5, 1930 and December 3, 1930 earthquake with the same magnitude. The former earthquake, well-known Bago earthquake, caused 50 deaths and great damages in Yangon while 500 casualties were resulted in Bago. The other significant earthquakes are Yangon earthquakes of September 10, 1927 and December 17, 1927. These events also resulted in a certain amount of damage in

Yangon (Myo Thant et al., 2015). According to probabilistic seismic hazard map of Yangon City (Myo Thant et al., 2015), the city is generally located in the zone of peak ground acceleration, PGA 0.29g – 0.5g as shown in the following Fig. 1. The seismicity of the area and some soils in Yangon City are highly susceptible to liquefaction, it is very important to have at least a general idea as to where liquefaction might occur.

Yangon City has experienced a large population and economic growth in the past few years. It also seems reasonable that this trend will continue for a number of years to come. City and county planners will be making many decisions about the growth and development within the city. Therefore, all types of information concerning the city will need to be considered in making wise choices of where to place industries, subdivisions, utilities and businesses. The mapping of ground damage severity index (DSI) would aid the planners and developers in their site selections and the level of analysis and design that a specific site might need. The liquefaction potential map could be a useful planning tool for various groups. The methods of analysis include historical research, liquefaction analysis (Seed and Idriss, 1971), liquefaction effect index (Iwasaki et al.), assessing ground damage severity classes (Bray et al.) and GIS technologies studies.

Fig. 1 Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Map of Yangon City, Yagon Region, for 10 % probability of exceedance in 50 years, in terms of peak ground acceleration (PGA) in g. (Myo Thant et al., 2015)

DATA COLLECTION

The area of Yangon City is organized with 35 Townships. According to the data obtained, 77 projects have been selected with 115 boreholes in total as shown in Fig. 2. The 30 boreholes were collected from Earthquake Risk Assessment Project under Myanmar Earthquake Committee, 72 boreholes had been taken from Geo-Friends Engineering and Construction Co. Ltd and 13 boreholes were got from Suntec Technologies Co. Ltd. The properties of resulted soil type in each site were applied in liquefaction analysis. The borehole location map and damage severity index map (DSI) were performed by using Geographic Information System (GIS).

Fig. 2 Boreholes Location Map of Yangon City

PROCEDURE OF LIQUEFACTION ANALYSIS

Liquefaction analysis is performed by the methods presented by “Architectural Foundation Design Guideline” (Japan Architectural Association, 1997) and Seed et al. (1985). According to Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Map of Yangon City, the seismic hazard in term of peak ground acceleration, PGA (in g) for recurrence interval in 475 years (10 % probability of exceedance in 50 years) is shown in Fig. 1. The PGA ranged from 0.29 to 0.5 g and the maximum seismic hazard zone comprises the eastern part of Yangon, East Dagon, South Dagon and Dagon Myothit Seikkan (PGA – 0.4 g to 0.5 g). Other wards of Yangon are in the PGA zone of 0.3 g to 0.4 g (Myo Thant et al., 2015).

(1) Object Soil Layers for Liquefaction Analysis

(a) Depth of Soil Layers: GL \pm 0.0 to -20 meters

(b) Clay Content P_c : $P_c \leq 20\%$

(c) Fine Content F_c : $F_c < 35\%$ (However, even if $F_c \geq 35\%$, the soil which has $P_c \leq 10\%$ or $I_p \leq 15\%$ is analyzed for Liquefaction.)

(2) Calculation of Cyclic Stress Ratio (CSR)

According to Seed and Idriss (1971), Milutin Srbulov (2008), the cyclic stress ratio is calculated according to the following formula:

$$CSR = \frac{\tau}{\sigma'_v} = 0.65 \cdot \frac{a_{p,h}}{g} \cdot \frac{\sigma_v}{\sigma'_v} \cdot r_d \quad (1)$$

$$CSR = \frac{\tau}{\sigma'_v} = \text{Cyclic Stress Ratio}$$

$a_{p,h}$ = Peak Horizontal Ground Acceleration

g = Acceleration due to gravity

σ_v = Total vertical stress

σ'_v = Vertical effective stress

r_d = Stress factor with depth = $1 - (0.012 z)$ (Kayen et al., 1992) (2)

z = Depth from ground surface (GL in meter)

(3) Calculation of Cyclic Resistance Ratio (CRR)

A measured SPT blow count N can be normalized to an overburden pressure of 100 kPa according to Liao and Whitman (1986), and can be corrected to an energy ratio of 60% (the average ratio of the actual energy delivered by hammer to theoretical free-fall energy).

$$N_{60} = \frac{E_m C_B C_S C_{RN}}{0.6} \quad (3)$$

$$(N_1)_{60} = N_{60} C_N \quad (4)$$

$$C_N = \sqrt{\frac{100}{\sigma'_v}} < 2 \quad (5)$$

$(N_1)_{60}$ = Corrected SPT N-value to an energy ratio of 60%

N = Filed SPT N-value

σ'_v = Effective overburden pressure

CRR shall be determined by the following graph in Fig. 3 or the following equation which are developed for an earthquake magnitude of 7.5.

$$CRR = \frac{1}{34 - (N_1)_{60}} + \frac{(N_1)_{60}}{135} + \frac{50}{[10(N_1)_{60} + 45]^2} - \frac{1}{200} \quad (6)$$

For other magnitudes, the CRR values shall be multiplied by the magnitude scaling factor indicated in Table. 1 or shall be evaluated by following equation:

$$CRR_7 = CRR_{M=7.5} \times MSF \quad (7)$$

$$MSF = 10^{2.24} \times M_w^{-2.56} \quad (8)$$

$$CRR_{6.5} = CRR_{M=7.5} \times MSF \quad (9)$$

$$MSF = 10^3 \times M_w^{-3.46} \quad (10)$$

Table. 1: Magnitude correction factors (Ambraseys, 1988 & Eurocode 8 – 5)

Magnitude (M_w)	5.5	6.0	6.5	7.0	8.0
The Correction Factor	2.86	2.20	1.69	1.30	0.67

Fig. 3 Cyclic Resistant Ratio (CRR) versus corrected N-value

(4) Calculation of Safety Factor (FS) against Liquefaction

The Factor of Safety (FS) against liquefaction shall be determined as:

$$FS = \frac{CRR}{CSR} \quad (11)$$

CRR = Cyclic Resistance Ratio

CSR = Cyclic Stress Ratio

The above equation and charts are only designed for the earthquake of magnitude 7.5. Hence the adjusted CRR value must be used to obtain the safety factors for other magnitude earthquakes. Generally, if $FS > 1.0$, there will be no possibility of occurrence of liquefaction. However, even if $FS > 1.0$, strain of soil might be appeared due to generation of excess pore water pressure by earthquake.

(5) Determination of Liquefaction Effect Index (I_L)

Liquefaction effect index (I_L) is a single-valued parameter to evaluate regional liquefaction affection. I_L at a site is computed by integrating the factors of safety (FS) along the soil column between 20m depth. A weighting function is added to give more weight to the layers closer to the ground surface. The liquefaction effect index (I_L) proposed by (Iwasaki et al.) is expressed as follows:

$$I_L = \int_0^{20} F_1 W_{(z)} dz \quad (12)$$

where F_1 is an index defined as: $F_1 = 1 - F_s$, if $F_s \leq 1.0$; and $F_1 = 0$ if $F_s > 1.0$, where F_s is the factor of safety against liquefaction triggering. The integration in Eq. (12) is carried out from the ground surface ($z = 0$) to the depth of 20 m, the depth below which the effect of liquefaction on the failure potential of the ground is considered negligible. The $W_{(z)}$ is a weighting function of depth, which is used to account for the effect of soil liquefaction at different depths to the failure potential of the ground. The weighting function is assumed by Iwasaki et al. to be a linear function of depth z (in meters):

$$W_{(z)} = 10 - 0.5 z \quad (13)$$

Note that the index (I_L) defined by Iwasaki et al. was meant to reflect the effect of liquefaction. He proposed the following criteria for assessing liquefaction-induced ground failure potential: (a) no failure potential if $I_L = 0$, (b) low potential if $0 < I_L \leq 5$, (c) high potential if $5 < I_L \leq 15$, and (d) extremely high potential if $I_L > 15$. The Iwasaki method is *in principle* quite attractive as it deals directly with the liquefaction effect that is the subject of field observations. The same view has been expressed by other researchers [Ref: 10].

GROUND DAMAGE SEVERITY INDEX (DSI)

The severity of liquefaction-induced ground damage may be grouped into three classes according to the observed surface damage in post-earthquake investigations (Juang et al. 2005). The severity of ground damage may be judged based on the observed sand boil, settlement, lateral movement, and tilting and collapse of buildings. Three classes of damage severity, as shown in Table. 2, are used herein for grouping case histories. They are ‘no damage’ (defined with a damage severity index, **DSI**, of **1**), ‘minor to moderate damage’, if **DSI = 2**, and ‘major damage’, if **DSI = 3** (Juang et al. 2005). These classes are slight modifications of those defined

by Bray et al. The liquefaction effect value (Iwasaki et al.) had been calibrated by Juang et al. 2005, which based on quality field damage observation from his paper. The following classification criteria are proposed for assessing ground damage severity:

DSI = 1, if $I_L \leq 5$

DSI = 2, if $5 < I_L \leq 12$

DSI = 3, if $I_L > 12$

Table. 2 Liquefaction-induced Damage Severity Classes at Foundations

Class of Severity	Description	Interpretation
DSI = 1	No observed ground damage	No settlement, no tilt, and no lateral movement or sand boils
DSI = 2	Minor to moderate ground damage	Settlement < 25 cm, tilt of buildings < 3°, lateral movement <10cm
DSI = 3	Major ground damage	Settlement ≥ 25 cm, tilt of buildings ≥ 3°, or lateral movement ≥ 10 cm, or collapse of buildings

DSI = damage severity index.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Following the analysis, the maps of areas susceptible to liquefaction damage were drawn up with GIS technologies, classifying these as no observed ground damage, minor to moderate ground damage and major ground damage that corresponding as **DSI 1**, **DSI 2** and **DSI 3** respectively. According to the data obtained, 77 projects have been selected with 115 boreholes in total and many places of southern Yangon are occurred major ground damage which can be seen in Fig. 4. According to result, large portions of Yangon City especially in downtown are subject to liquefaction at the highest level of magnitude (Mw:7), many of them with probability over 60% according to I_L values. This high damage includes the alluvial deposits adjacent to Port of Yangon. Given the significant city wide potential for liquefaction type failure, this failure would be a key damage mechanism during the earthquake. At a

magnitude of 7, much of the area has an elevated probability of liquefaction at the 475-year return period PGA values. Southern part of Yangon City is higher than Northern part that because of mostly Quaternary Alluvial Deposits (Win Naing, 1996) and Lower Water-level. Northern part is located hilly region and mainly composed of Shale & Sandstone rock units (Win Naing, 1996). **DSI 1** and **DSI 2** classes can be seen in the heart of City. No observed ground damage is probably located on Anticlinal Ridge and eastern part of Yangon is caused by soil conditions (Silty Soil < Clayey Soil). Western part of city is damaged by low water level conditions (2-4m, SPT Data). All of the final result can be observed in Fig. 4.

SUMMARY & RECOMMENDATION

This paper has developed three types of liquefaction-induced ground damage classes using geotechnical data and index distribution map that can be applied for evaluation of hazard and risk posed to Yangon City by liquefaction during seismic events. This was performed by SPT-data and using GIS technologies. Considering the high importance of Yangon City, this study attempts to evaluate the factors of safety against liquefaction (FS) and corresponding liquefaction effect index (I_L) for the worst seismic scenario for the city using SPT-based semi-empirical procedure and attempts to produce index maps that can be estimate for liquefaction potential. The DSI classes shows the liquefaction-induced vulnerability at different sites in the city. Liquefaction-induced ground damage for sites with $I_L > 15$ is major damage, and no damage is very unlikely at sites with $I_L \leq 5$. I_L is greater than 15 for $M_w = 7$ at many sites in the downtown of city as Fig. 4. The final result of mapping that was showing southern part of Yangon City is higher damage than northern part. Northern part of city is built on hilly region and mainly composed of Shale & Sandstone rock units (Win Naing, 1996). Minor damage of city is mainly located on Anticlinal Ridge and most of the damage in eastern is caused by soil conditions (Silty Soil < Clayey Soil) and western part is caused by low water level conditions (2 - 4m, SPT Data).

The development of liquefaction-induced ground damage severity index mapping provides an insight into a seismic hazard that exists in Yangon City. It is recommended that the damage map from this study can be used in planning and development decisions that are made in connection with the growth of the city. A second recommendation would be the improvement and updating of the potential map as new information is made available. New boring logs would provide valuable information that could be used in refining the potential

map. New and additional groundwater information such as the depth and locations of perched water tables would also be important in further refinement of the potential map. Additional information on the seismicity of the area and newly geological data should also be obtained to improve the liquefaction potential map.

Fig. 4 Liquefaction-induced Ground Damage Severity Index (DSI) Map of Yangon City

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